

USAGE OF MODERN METHODS IN TEACHING ENGLISH

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Abstract: This article discusses various types of effective and modern methods of teaching English and using them in professional English which mitigate learning process.

Keywords: teaching, effective methods, technology and learners.

Anotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada professional ta'limda ingliz tilini o'qitishda foydalaniladigan va o'rganish jarayonini yengillashtiradigan bir qancha samarali va zamonaviy metodlar xususida so'z boradi.

Kalit so'zlar: o'qitish, samarali metodlar, texnologiya va o'rganuvchi.

Аннотация: В данной статье рассматриваются различные виды эффективных и современных методов преподавания английского языка и их использование в профессиональном английском языке, которые облегчают процесс обучения.

Ключевые слова: обучение, эффективные методы, технологии и учащиеся.

Today, in our developing society, great importance is attached to foreign languages. In particular, the number of English language learners among young people has increased dramatically in recent years. In addition, the English language has become the main component of the professional education of people who become mature personnel in each field. English language learners can be acquired in educational institutions and various training courses to study language. The students' excellent language learning is dependent on the teacher's teaching ability and the teaching aids he/she uses.

As the 21st century is the age of technology, many conveniences have been created for consumers. These technologies and innovations have revolutionized not only our daily life but also the education system. Through modern innovations, teaching and learning foreign languages became much easier and began to give effective results. An innovative approach ensures that students are more involved in the learning process, satisfied with various teaching methods, and ultimately turns the learning process into an interesting and useful experience. Living in the age of technology, relying only on the blackboard and

the textbook in the course and lesson, it is equivalent to looking at one's work irresponsibly.

Here are some methods of interactive English teaching that helped we,students to learn English fast:

Gamification----is a method of making regular learning processes or teaching activities more interesting and useful by adding game mechanics and elements. Kahoot! And organizing games using applications like Quizizz helps students to improve their vocabulary knowledge and they have features such as motivation spirit, active participation in the lessons and good memory recall of the lesson.

1As we can see, the communicative method leads to the gamification method, which is considered as a tool used in the classroom today due to the progress of new technologies.

2. In addition to engaging the reader in an active and interesting role for him, this approach allows us to explain several things according to Negre (2017).

This methodological approach allows the student to:

- a) Ability to adapt to any educational program.
- b) development of cooperation and teamwork.
- c) Develop critical thinking and problem solving skills.
- d) Improving communication skills.
- e) Be aware of the challenges that should be faced
- f) formation of deductive thinking.
- g) Learning to work under team leadership.
- h) to be heroes of learning; It also has a playful component.

2) Flipped classroom---- is one of the modern approaches to the organization of the educational process, in which educational processes are carried out in reverse order. This model is widely used as an innovative and effective approach to language teaching. In this method, in contrast to the traditional lesson structure, the student learns new knowledge outside the classroom (independently), and the time in the classroom is mainly spent on practical training, communication and exercises. Students learn grammar rules, new words, and language skills through video lessons, podcasts, or study materials before class. During the class, they apply this knowledge in real situations through communication, role-plays, written work and discussions. This allows the teacher to identify which students have not mastered the lesson well and to help them individually to teach the lesson better.

Today, modern computer technologies are used in almost all areas of human activity. It is in the teaching of English that these technologies play a major role, and through this the teacher organizes modern lessons. The use of technology and various applications during the lesson increases students' motivation to learn English, ensures equal active participation in the lesson and helps to organize the lesson process in an interesting way. Currently, in the process of teaching English, Duolingo, Mesmerize, Lingq, kahoot! And Quizlet is a very popular app and online platform. These apps help students improve their vocabulary, do grammar exercises, use flash cards, participate actively through tests and quizzes, and make classes fun.

3) Language learning begins with listening and speaking, so storytelling is a fabulous tool for teaching any language. Storytelling in classes is not just talking and listening to the basic narrative. It also provides students with a lot of opportunities to practice their skills by completing various student-centered tasks. Storytelling may be the focal point in language classes, and teachers can build wonderful extensions around it. There are numerous engaging pre-storytelling activities, such as describing pictures and making predictions and personal connections in which students get intrigued and motivated to participate. There are various post-storytelling tasks too, including role-plays, answering questions, making alternative endings of the story, etc. This could be a perfect moment for students to harmonize and filter everything they have heard and learned and give their final touch. Storytelling and drama in teaching English are the most powerful tool, as they create engaging, immersion and effective learning experiences. These methods are especially effective for students of all ages and proficiency levels, as they make language learning more enjoyable and meaningful. Benefits of Storytelling in teaching language that stories provide a natural context for language, helping students understand vocabulary and grammar in use. According to researchers listening to stories help students improve comprehension and listening abilities.

We all know that education is one of the most important areas and that it is constantly developing and improving. "Education is the passport to the future, because tomorrow belongs to those who prepare for it today." So learning English can open a wide range of opportunities and benefits for us. Such as, education opportunities like access to international universities, scholarships and even exchange programs. Besides that, if you already graduated you can read research papers, books and online resources that are mostly in English. Learning language always benefits you to achieve your purposes in life.

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